

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D1.5: Minutes of 2nd Advisory Board meetings

WP1 – Project Management

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1 Executive summary

The purpose of the current deliverable is to document the liaison that has taken place with the STEP External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) and the recommendations that these experts have provided to the project consortium from M4 until M14. The first meeting with the EEAB was held in M3, while the most important points discussed during this meeting were reported in D1.2-Minutes of 1st Advisory Board meeting.

Regarding the structure of the current document, in Chapter 2 a short introduction on the role of the EEAB within the STEP project is provided, while in Chapter 3 new members who entered the board from M4 until M14 are presented. The meetings held during this period between EEAB members and STEP partners are presented in Chapter 4, and, finally, some of the most important recommendations of the experts to the STEP partners are summarized in Chapter 5 accompanied with the actions taken by the consortium to address these points.

2 Introduction

For the strategic goal of coordination and integration of different disciplinary fields and expertise in the project, a fruitful communication and information exchange with external experts of relevant fields is crucial. This process involves both the project consortium and the EEAB. The EEAB serves as external adviser to the STEP consortium in order to reach the predefined targets and consolidate the project results as best as possible. The STEP partners are continuously providing the EEAB with the appropriate project information and support in the production of their advice and recommendations. The EEAB assists the STEP partners with independent strategic recommendations on the project objectives and long term developments.

3 Update of the EEAB list

The creation and management of the EEAB is a dynamic procedure throughout the whole duration of the project. Thus, new members are added when it is necessary. In M3, the EEAB consisted of 5 members as described in D1.2-Minutes of 1st Advisory Board meeting. These people are experts in the fields of youth participation, user engagement, environment, and policy making. However, as the project evolved, the STEP partners identified the need to include in the EEAB an expert in data protection (Dr. Eva Lievens), internet and social media (Mr. Joakim Jardenberg), and youth affairs (Ms. Eva Theisz). Moreover, a representative of a Greek public authority was added to the EEAB (Mr. Babis Tsitlakidis) to ensure that the developed solution responds to the market needs. A short description of the qualifications of the new members of the STEP EEAB is presented below:

Eva Lievens

Eva Lievens is a Professor of Law and Technology at the Law Faculty of Ghent University. Previously, she was a member of the KU Leuven Centre for IT and IP Law from 2003 until 2015. Her research focuses on legal challenges posed by new media and ICT phenomena, with a specific focus on the protection of minors, fundamental rights and alternative regulatory instruments. She holds a law degree from the University of Ghent (2002), a Masters degree in Transnational Communications and Global Media from Goldsmiths College, London (2003) and a Phd in Law from KU Leuven (2009).

Joakim Jardenberg

Joakim Jardenberg is Internet and Social Media Expert at Helsingborg, Sweden. He has been appointed “expert” by the Swedish Prime minister and worked with him at the Northern Future Forum, while his website(<http://jardenberg.se>) has been awarded as the “most influential blog on media, PR and advertising” by Cision. He has strong experience as advisor and investor for successful technical platform startups such as Fortnox and Videoplaza.

Eva Theisz

Eva Theisz is Director of Support and Cooperation at the Swedish Agency for Youth and Civil Society, a government agency that aims to ensure that young people have access to influence and welfare and support the government in issues relevant to civil society policy. She is responsible for distribution of state and EU funds to the civil society in the form of support for organisations, projects and international cooperation.

Babis Tsitlakidis

Babis Tsitlakidis is Chief Digital Officer of the Municipality of Thessaloniki. He is in charge of the eGovernment and Digital Transformation procedures in the operational planning of the Municipality. He has been member of the coordination team of the three crowdsourcing initiatives of the Municipality (Apps4Thessaloniki, Hackathess and Apps4Thessaloniki – Tourism Edition) and member of the evaluation committee of the latter two. He is also member of the Steering Committees of the eParticipation project

[Improve My City](#).

The full list of the EEAB members as it is formed so far can be found in ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB, while short CVs of these members are also provided in the [STEP website](#).

4 Meetings

At an early stage of the project (M3), a conference call between the STEP partners and all members of the STEP EEAB was held in order to introduce STEP project partners and EEAB members to each other, to inform EEAB members about the project and the challenges the consortium faces, and to offer the STEP consortium the chance to elicit some initial crucial recommendations for the implementation of the project. After this initial contact, the consortium agreed that from that moment individual meetings with each member of the EEAB will be held when they are needed so that the consortium elicits in-depth recommendations for any emerging issue.

In this framework, the following meetings were organised:

- Kerstin Franzl, coordinator of the EUth project and expert in youth participation, participated in the 2nd day of the 3rd STEP project meeting in Mollet del Valles, Spain on the 12th of February 2016. Specifically, she briefly presented the EUth project, the EUth project management

online toolbox that will be available by the end of the year, and a general overview of the EUth dissemination strategy. Finally, she pointed some of the most important lessons learnt from her experience of setting up and managing public participation processes.

- Babis Tsitlakidis, Chief Digital Officer at the Municipality of Thessaloniki, participated in the 4th STEP project meeting in Heraklion, Greece on the 29th of June 2016. During the meeting, he presented some of the digital platforms that the Municipality of Thessaloniki uses until now, and how they apply eParticipation approaches. He expressed the willingness of the Municipality of Thessaloniki to test and adopt the STEP platform when it will be launched. Finally, Babis explained the benefits that his Municipality will gain by using the STEP platform and how they will integrate it in their existing platforms.
- Christodoulos Keratidis and Panagiota Syropoulou (DRAXIS), Mustafa Serdar Yümlü (SAMPAS), and Soiris Diplaris (CERTH) had a conference call with Eva Lievens, Professor of Law and Technology at the Law Faculty of Ghent University, on the 8th of July 2016. The purpose of the call was to discuss potential data protection issues that may arise throughout the duration of the project.

The recommendations that the EEAB members suggested during the above meetings are presented in the following Chapter.

5 Recommendations and actions

This Chapter focuses on the most important points raised and concluded during the meetings described in Chapter 4.

1) Ms. Franzl pointed that time is needed to build trust between the consortium and public authorities and between citizens and public authorities. She also pointed that we should be careful to launch a well prepared product so that we build trust with users and convince them to participate in more challenges.

< The STEP consortium is in constant contact with the public authorities that will pilot test the platform. Thus, trust has been built between the project partners and the public authorities. Additionally, the consortium will take into account the need of trust building between citizens and public authorities during the pilot planning procedure and will ensure that there will be no information gaps between different challenges.>

2) Ms. Franzl recommended to consider public participation as a means of change in culture and she mentioned that we should balance a project-based approach versus a structure-based approach.

<In STEP, we do not deem the participation procedures that will be executed through the STEP platform as individual projects, but as a general approach that will enable public authorities to gain experience and set the structure and the procedures that should be followed in the future.>

3) Ms. Franzl also mentioned that we should take into account that young people have short attention span.

< The challenges that will be executed through the STEP platform will be of short duration (~6 months) to keep youth engaged.>

4) Another key issue that Ms. Franzl pointed was the fact that young people tend to be influenced by their peers.

<It will be suggested to the pilot partners to use young people from their authorities to locally disseminate the project.>

5) Ms. Franzl also emphasized that, regarding dissemination, the best practice is to combine online and offline activities, but ensure that the information from the offline events are entered to the platform so that we do not have any information gaps.

<This remark has already been taken into account in the design of the STEP local dissemination plans. Online and offline dissemination activities will be organized throughout the whole duration of the project, while info kiosks will be placed outside the venue of the launch events for those with no internet access, and special dissemination material will be designed and distributed.>

6) Finally, Ms. Franzl pointed that public authorities should be careful with the online moderation of the content of the STEP platform.

<In the framework of the local pilots planning, different responsibilities have been assigned to the involved public servants, among which a specific person will be responsible to moderate the content of the platform.>

7) Mr. Tsitlakidis suggested that public authorities should give strong motives (even prizes) to young people so that they participate in decision making procedures.

<All partners agreed that young people will receive feedback on how their opinion will be taken into account. Each pilot partner will decide on specific incentives that will be offered to the participants in their area.>

8) Regarding privacy policies and terms and conditions of the STEP platform, Ms. Lievens mentioned that young people understand and respond better on content with visualization features rather than on plain text. She also provide the STEP consortium with an interesting article with regard to novel approached to privacy policies (<http://firstmonday.org/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/4010>).

<The STEP partners will consider to add appealing visualization features to the STEP terms and conditions.>

9) Ms. Lievens also recommended to the consortium to take into account the following:

- Children/ young people may have difficulties with regard to understanding privacy policies and terms and conditions. An article relevant to this topic was provided by Ms. Lievens (<http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/full/10.1108/info-06-2014-0026>).
- A new European Accessibility Act is being prepared (http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-15-6147_en.htm). There is also a proposal for a Directive on the accessibility of public sector bodies' websites (http://eur-lex.europa.eu/procedure/EN/2012_340).
- A new data protection legislation has been adopted (http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.119.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2016:119:TOC and http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/reform/index_en.htm).
- The national Data Protection Authority of the country where the data is processed should be notified (http://ec.europa.eu/justice/policies/privacy/docs/international_transfers_faq/international_transfers_faq.pdf). As Turkey is not an "adequate country", it is advised to data controllers to "check with their national data protection authority whether additional third countries, specific data transfer

operations or sets of data transfer operations to third countries are considered adequate according to their national data protection legislation".

- Regarding data transfers to Turkey, a specific Data Protection Act entered into force in Turkey since the 7th of April 2016 (<http://blogs.dlapiper.com/privacymatters/turkey-new-data-protection-law/>) (also with information about data transfer out of Turkey, something which apparently was not possible before this Act).

<The consortium will take into account all the above remarks and will update deliverable D2.3 ("Guidelines for ethical legal issues and data protection") if necessary.>

6 Conclusions

Since the very beginning of the project, the STEP partners have close collaboration with the members of the EEAB in order to learn from their experience and consolidate the project results. From M4 until M14, four new members were added to the board to cover the fields of data protection, internet and social media, youth affairs, and public authorities' perspective. Up to now, the EEAB consists of nine members. During this period, three individual meetings with some of them were organized offering to the consortium the chance to acquire interesting recommendations for the successful implementation and future exploitation of the project. All these recommendations will be addressed by the project partners throughout the duration of the project. The next meetings with the EEAB members will be held throughout the duration of the project when need of consultation will emerge.

ANNEX A - Members of the EEAB

Name	Location	Position	Personal website
Ms. Kerstin Franzl	Berlin, Germany	Coordinator of the project EUth	http://goo.gl/LuTtRe
Dr. Catriona Macaulay	Edinburgh, UK	Head of User Research and Engagement at The Scottish Government	https://www.linkedin.com/in/catmacaulay
Dr. Enric Coll Gelabert	Barcelona, Spain	Environmental Technician at Environmental Education and Promotion Office of the Barcelona Provincial Council	-
Mr. Epameinondas Christofilopoulos	Thessaloniki, Greece	Horizon 2020 National Expert for Climate Change	https://goo.gl/clZ1Yc
Dr. Eva Lievens	Leuven, Belgium	Professor of Law and Technology at the Law Faculty of Ghent University	https://goo.gl/khlOMZ
Mr. Joakim Jardnberg	Helsingborg, Sweden	Internet and Social Media Expert at Helsingborg	https://goo.gl/OuKGAQ
Ms. Eva Theisz	Stockholm, Sweden	Director of Support and Cooperation at the Swedish Agency for Youth and Civil Society	http://goo.gl/UVOlny
Ms. Christiane Klemm	Greifswald, Germany	Board Member of Youth and Environment Europe	http://goo.gl/hUibce
Mr. Babis Tsitlakidis	Thessaloniki, Greece	Chief Digital Officer at Municipality of Thessaloniki	https://goo.gl/ogFR6y